

METHODOLOGY FOR IMPROVING THE COMMUNICATIVE
TRAINING OF EDUCATORS THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF
EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

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Annotation: the article considers the need for the presence and development of emotional intelligence in the teacher as one of the main factors of self-realization and success in professional activities. Five main components of emotional intelligence are shown. The trend has also been shown to be particularly well observed in the modern, postindustrial development of society, particularly in higher education. The emotional intelligence of the teacher is analyzed the factor of improving the teacher training system, the condition of the social adaptation of students at the Pedagogical University, the quality of education in higher education and the positive practices of the formation of emotional intelligence in the university environment, and the ways and features of the development of emotional intelligence of future teachers are revealed.

Keywords: emotional intelligence , modern teacher , pedagogical skills, emotional intelligence, efficiency, components, competence, higher education.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается необходимость наличия и развития эмоционального интеллекта у педагога как один из основных факторов самореализации и успеха в профессиональной деятельности. Показаны пять основных компонентов эмоционального интеллекта. Также было показано, что эта тенденция особенно хорошо наблюдается в современном постиндустриальном развитии общества, особенно в сфере

высшего образования. Эмоциональный интеллект учителя анализируется как фактор совершенствования системы подготовки учителей, условие социальной адаптации студентов в педагогическом университете, повышение качества образования в высшем образовании и позитивные практики формирования эмоционального интеллекта в университетской среде, выявляются пути и особенности развития эмоционального интеллекта будущих учителей.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональный интеллект, современный учитель , педагогическое мастерство , эмоциональный интеллект, эффективность, компоненты, компетентность, высшее образование.

The study of emotional intelligence of a person has a relatively short history in local and world psychology and pedagogy. The history of the development of most of the problems classified in this research area dates back a little over a decade [1, 4]. However, in recent times, such topics have become significantly relevant . This trend is not surprising, considering that modern society has made the following requirements for its members:

- ✓ increase responsibility for their actions and decisions;
- ✓ initiative in the process of interaction with other members of society.

In connection with the above, another important requirement of society that is imposed on the individual at the present stage of its development. This means that the latter must have maximum awareness of its development needs in order to successfully achieve the goals pursued, without violating the rights and freedoms of other members of society. In turn, such actions are associated with the ability of a modern person to understand the feelings of others, and therefore analyze his own emotional experiences. In other words, one of the main requirements that modern society, including the educator, places on the individual, is the existence of a formed emotional intelligence [7, 10]. At the present stage of the development of this topic, emotional intelligence can be defined as the type of

intelligence responsible for recognizing personal emotions and the emotions of others, as well as managing them [4, 7]. This author claims that emotional abilities are not innate talents, but skills that a person can learn throughout his life. Thus, to some extent, we can say with confidence that emotional abilities are qualities that a modern specialist, in particular a teacher, can purposefully develop through practice. Emotional intelligence has been described as a structure divided into five areas. A number of foreign authors argue that an adequate development of emotional intelligence in the implementation of professional activities allows a specialist to achieve three important results:

1. High productivity.
2. Excellent leadership qualities.
3. Being able to create conditions for happiness.

In connection with the above, we can note that the presence of developed emotional intelligence in the teacher is one of the important conditions for the successful modernization of modern higher education. For example, as for the first of the above results - increasing the effectiveness of the teacher's professional activity, it should be noted that emotional abilities to achieve high-quality pedagogical activity in some cases are not inferior to knowledge, skills and skills. and abilities directly related to the teaching profession [8, 53].

Developed emotional intelligence, as mentioned above, can also contribute to the development of leadership qualities in the teacher. The development of the emotional intelligence of the teacher is associated with his emotional culture. The latter reflects his emotional maturity, as well as the level of professional skill that affects his image. It is later known that the teaching profession is transformative and managerial in terms of its place in the educational system [8, 69]. In order to effectively manage student personality development, it is necessary to have appropriate competence. Therefore, in accordance with the personality-oriented

approach to education and upbringing, the development of the emotional culture of teachers is of particular importance.

The most important indicator of the development of the emotional culture of a modern teacher is the high level of development of the following qualities:

1. sympathy;
2. emotional stability;
3. emotional flexibility.

In turn, emotional stability is the ability of an individual to resist unfavorable factors, eliminate the state of emotional arousal and quickly return to a state of mental balance after experiencing a stressful situation. This last quality is an important factor in ensuring the normal functioning of a modern teacher and its effective interaction with other participants in the educational process. Emotional flexibility is manifested in the teacher's ability to correctly understand the experience of students, receive sincere, warm to them and participate. Empathy involves the reflection and understanding of the emotional state of another person, empathy or empathy for others, and actively helping behavior. It is based on intelligence, emotional sensitivity and rational perception of the environment [9, 24].

Scientists have adopted emotional intelligence as part of a person's social intelligence, which determines his ability to communicate and socialize. However, an in - depth study of the emotional sphere of a person began much earlier-in 1986 by Wayne Paine with the publication "The Study of emotion: the development of emotional intelligence", which he proposed to test emotional intelligence using the coefficient of emotionality. At the same time, the identification of emotionality was similar in many ways to the diagnosis of human intelligence [7, 38].

Currently, there are two accepted models of emotional intelligence proposed by Daniel Goleman and Peter Salovey and John Mayer. The first model involves a systematic review of emotional intelligence, while the second focuses on the

procedural side of this phenomenon. D. The Goleman model includes five components of emotional intelligence, specifically:

- 1) understanding or understanding one's own feelings;
- 2) control your emotions;
- 3) self-stimulation;
- 4) understanding or understanding the feelings of others;
- 5) relationship management (i.e. control of the feelings of others) [4, 315].

The process model encompasses four aspects of emotional intelligence, including relevant social competencies: the differentiation of emotions, the perception of existing emotions, the management of the emotional sphere, the use of acquired knowledge. It is very important for the teacher to have a flexible psyche and developed emotional intelligence, which helps to find solutions to complex situations of communication. However, with increasing professional experience, this skill is often deformed and, as a result, completely blurred by teachers who use stereotypical methods to deal with pedagogical situations [2, 151]. Analyzing the aggressive behavior of schoolchildren, he concludes that the age of the teacher does not affect his attitude towards students, but that the decisive factor is his gender and work experience. At the same time, teachers who have worked in schools for a long time and have great pedagogical experience are distinguished by their rejection of students' opinions, while young teachers are distinguished by their high commitment to the creative manifestations of adolescents [3, 78].

The developed emotional intelligence of the teacher, on the contrary, allows him to feel stable and comfortable in the conditions of a constantly changing social environment. In addition, with the help of developed emotional intelligence, the teacher can predict the success of a certain pedagogical impact on students and build sufficient boundaries of communication with students, which allows not to over-mix with students, as well as avoid excessive coldness. teacher. Emotional

intelligence allows you to organize pedagogical communication, respecting the personal boundaries of the teacher and students. In the process of interaction between the student and the teacher, communication receives influencing and regulatory functions. Improper Organization of pedagogical communication leads to the fear of students, a lack of confidence in their own creative abilities, a weakening of attention, memory, work efficiency, and also negatively affects information and the ability to critically perceive the results of their work. The result of a wrong approach to the organization of communication between students and the teacher is a negative attitude towards the teacher, and then to educational activities as a whole [6, 109].

It should be noted that the emotional intelligence of the teacher largely determines the success of his professional career. Modern education provides students with the ability to develop creative abilities, creative and critical thinking, as well as independently search for information that allows them to solve educational problems. It can be said that the teacher's emotional intelligence, recognition of emotions, the ability to control the mental state and behavior of students stimulates the cognitive activity of students and is a motivation for educational activities. At the same time, the emotional reactions of the teacher precede his rational reactions, which, together with the intellectual sphere of the teacher, once again emphasizes the great importance of developing the emotional sphere. For example, in the process of modern education, situations arise that require the teacher to provide psychological assistance to students: a background of a decrease in the child's general activity occurs when students are involved in violence or violence by peers, when there is an unfavorable emotional atmosphere in the family or negative emotions arise against him.

Currently, domestic and foreign researchers are looking for effective methods that will help develop the emotional intelligence of teachers, reduce the nervous tension of teachers and adolescents. Scientists who adhere to a dispositional

approach to the main methods of developing the emotional intelligence of a teacher are based on the idea of the need to develop communication skills and confidence in their professional skills, as well as a tolerant attitude towards the participants in the educational process. Proponents of the temporary approach focus on the need to develop the teacher's ability to respond in a timely manner to pedagogical situations and organize psychological support for children when experiencing an age-related crisis or difficult life situations. A key aspect of the contextual approach is that teachers must adhere to the values of respectful treatment of each individual, regardless of their intellectual characteristics, and are themselves an example of this attitude towards students [7, 64].

Thus, emotional intelligence as a content-specific aspect of a teacher's effectiveness determines his ability to do the following: 1. Self-presentation in the team, which helps to develop the respectful attitude of students as an example of respectful attitude towards the subjects of the educational process. 2. It is necessary to identify and recognize the feelings of a child based on verbal and non-verbal information (gestures, facial expressions, children's posture), to regulate the emotional sphere of the child, to successfully carry out educational activities in order to ensure a favorable psychological atmosphere in the team. number of students. 3. In cases of emotional instability of the child, emotional stability helps the student to organize timely psychological assistance and solve his problem. The above facts and the author's reasoning allow us to timely respond to the existing pedagogical situations in the teacher and conclude that it is very important to develop emotional intelligence, which is an effective mechanism of teacher adaptation that allows students to stimulate successful educational activities.

Conclusion

Based on the above, we can say that in order to teach the specific competencies of the emotional intelligence of a modern teacher, the teacher must achieve a certain level of emotional intelligence. For teachers who are able to

control their emotions, it is much easier to be effective in stressful situations and develop competencies such as Initiative. It is also necessary to form emotional competencies to predict success at work. The development of emotional intelligence in teachers becomes even more important in modern conditions, considering that this feature can develop in people of any age category. Thus, through the development of emotional intelligence, a modern teacher can achieve high results in the professional sphere and become a highly effective specialist.

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